

A MICROMECHANICS-BASED FATIGUE LIFE PREDICTION APPROACH WITH OCTAGONAL FIBER MODEL FOR THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Fatigue tests were carried out on $[45/-45]_{2s}$ laminated composites, made of E-glass with sizing SE4740 and thermoplastic resin, in order to find its fatigue behavior. To theoretically predict the laminate response, a micromechanics-based fatigue life prediction approach, called MMFatigue, was proposed in this work, which was composed of two steps: macro stress analysis and micromechanics-based fatigue analysis. In the macro stress analysis, the ply stresses were derived from the laminate stresses using classical laminate theory. For the second step, an octagonal fiber model (OFM), was proposed to describe the micro structure, such that the micro fatigue stress in each constituent (fiber, matrix and interface) were calculated from ply stress. To convert multiaxial micro stresses to a uniaxial equivalent stress, a fatigue model was employed for each constituent. Then, a modified Goodman formulation of constant life diagram (CLD) was utilized to define constituent effective stress, which is a function of the mean value and amplitude of equivalent stress, as well as constituent strengths. Finally, the effective stress and fatigue life were correlated through experimentally obtained S-N curve for each constituent. To verify the accuracy of proposed approach, the prediction results were compared with test data of $[45/-45]_{2s}$ laminates. As an application, MMFatigue was applied to predict the thermoplastic wind turbine blade fatigue life, by comparing to the prediction using GL method to demonstrate the capability of the proposed approach. Besides, the fatigue tests and prediction of $[45/-45]_{2s}$ thermoset laminate composites were also performed to investigate the difference between thermoplastic and thermoset composites.

Key methodology and results:

The flow-chart for micromechanics based fatigue life prediction approach was shown in Figure 1. The incident fatigue loads were applied to the wind turbine blade to generate the laminate stress. Then, using classical laminate theory, the ply stresses were obtained. Next, the micro stresses in each constituent were calculated from ply stresses under the help of stress amplification factor (SAF). The equivalent stresses for each constituent were computed by different constituent fatigue models. A modified Goodman formulation for CLD was employed to each constituent to obtain the effective stress, then the fatigue life of each constituent was obtained. Figure 2 shows the comparison between the prediction and test data for thermoplastic and thermoset composites. From the results we can draw the conclusion that the thermoplastic resin shows better static and fatigue properties than thermoset resin with same sizing SE4740.

Figure 1: Flow-chart for micromechanics based fatigue life prediction approach.

Figure 2: Comparison between the prediction and test data for thermoplastic and thermoset composites.

REFERENCES

- [1] Huang, Y., Jin, K., Xu, L., Mustafa, G., Han, Y. and Ha, S., 2011. A MICROMECHANICAL METHODOLOGY FOR FATIGUE LIFE PREDICTION OF POLYMERIC MATRIX COMPOSITES. *In 18th International Conference on Composite Materials*.
- [2] Jin, K.K., Ghulam, M., Kim, J.H., Ha, S.K., López, B.M. and Gorostidi, A., 2009. Life prediction of wind turbine blades. *Brain Korea, 21*.